

1 **Tnfrsf8 silencing during germ layer lineage choice of pluripotent stem cells.**

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7 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
8 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
9 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
10 describe a requirement for silencing of Tnfrsf8 in germ layer lineage choice from pluripotent stem cells in
11 *Homo sapiens*.

12 Citations

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1. Hinterbrandner, M., Rubino, V., Stoll, C., Forster, S., Schnüriger, N., Radpour, R., Baerlocher, G.M., Ochsenbein, A.F. and Riether, C., 2021. Tnfrsf4-expressing regulatory T cells promote immune escape of chronic myeloid leukemia stem cells. JCI insight, 6(23), p.e151797.